

OCCURRENCE OF FAILURES WHEN DETERMINING THE RELIABILITY OF BOILERS AND INSTALLATIONS OPERATING WITH NATURAL GAS

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Abstract

The article describes possible failures that may occur during the operation of boilers and installations operating with natural gas. The possibilities of determining these refusals and the reasons for their occurrence are considered. Information is given to control and manage the risks leading to these failures, as an opportunity to predict their occurrence and create a basis for their dissipation or elimination in order to ensure the safe operation of boilers and installations working with natural gas.

Keywords: Industrial boilers; Risk assessment of industrial boilers; Steam boilers; Accidents and risks with steam and water boilers; failures in gas installations

1. Introduction

The reliability of the technical equipment, and in particular the boilers and installations working with natural gas as the main fuel, is essential to guarantee the safety when using these equipment, as equipment with increased danger. Reliability, this is the property of these facilities to preserve during their operation their parameters, characterizing the performance of their design definition functions, within certain limits and conditions of work, maintenance and storage. The ability of boilers and plants to remain operational until the limit state is reached together with interruptions required for service and repair constitutes their durability.

The main characteristic of reliability is the absence of failures or the so-called no-failure. This characteristic shows the property of boilers and installations working with natural gas to keep their process of working continuously for a certain period of time. If we consider the process of no failures from the point of view of control and management, it can be concluded that it is a process in which the instruments and control systems of boilers and installations maintain their stability and the quality of transient processes within permissible preset limits and for a certain period of time, while also not using any forced shutdowns and resumptions of normal operation after shutdowns.

As the main indicators for evaluating the absence of failures, we can introduce the following indicators:

- $Y(t)$ - Probability of failure-free operation for a predetermined time
- T_{cp} - Average uptime without failures
- $\lambda(t)$ - Intensity of refusals

2. Probability of failure-free operation of boilers and installations running on natural gas

The occurrence of failures is essentially a random event. If we consider the failure time „ T “ to start at some initial time t_0 , we can find that the continuous random variable that is best characterized from a probabilistic point of view by the integral-type distribution function.

$$Q(t) = Y\{T < t\} \quad (1)$$

- $Y\{T < t\}$ - this is the probability of failure in the boiler or plant before the set time t has elapsed

The time-to-failure integral-type function is also a reliability function, or more precisely, the probability of failure. $Y(t)$ varies between zero and one, as in the argument change interval ($0 \leq t \leq \infty$) it is non-decreasing, positive and continuous.

The probability of continuous operation for the time $(0;t)$, which is actually the probability that no failure will occur during the specified time t is defined as the opposite of Y .

$$Y(t) = 1 - Q(t) = Y(T \geq t) \quad (2)$$

The probability of failure-free operation and occurrence of failure can be determined by collecting sufficient experimental data in the process of operation of boilers and installations working with natural gas as the main fuel, and can be calculated as follows:

$$\int_0^{\infty} q(t) dt = Q(\infty) = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$Q^\alpha(t) = \frac{n(t)}{N_0} = \frac{n(t)}{N(t) + n(t)}; N_0 = N(t) + n(t) \quad (4)$$

where

- α - this is the statistical qualifier
- $N(t)$ - number of elements of the boilers/installations that have worked properly up to that point
- $n(t)$ - number of items that have failed up to time t
- N_0 - number of items included in the study

The probability of failure-free operation starts at unity, tends to zero at $t \rightarrow \infty$ and is an increasing function of its argument (Figure 1).

Figure 1

3. Intensity of failures in boilers and natural gas installations

Over time, the operation of boilers and natural gas installations, as well as their elements, become less and less reliable, i.e. their reliability decreases with some intensity called the failure intensity and known as the λ -characteristic.

From a technical point of view, this characteristic can be interpreted as a degree of reliability at any point in time. From a statistical point of view, the λ -characteristic is defined as the ratio between the number of elements that have failed in a given time interval and the number of elements that have operated normally and without failure in that same time interval.

$$\lambda(t)^\alpha = \frac{n(\Delta t)}{N(\Delta t)} \quad (5)$$

where
 - $n(\Delta t)$ - number of items that failed the time interval $(t;t+\Delta t)$
 - $N(\Delta t)$ - normally operating items in the time interval $(t;t+\Delta t)$

- The λ -characteristic is directly related to the integral functions of failure and uptime probabilities.

The basis for these claims is the fact that, based on the dependence (5), the intensity of failures is introduced as a ratio of the rate of change of reliability to the level of reliability at the point. In a similar sense, λ is the ratio of the first derivative of the reliability to the reliability function at time t .

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{Q'(t)}{Y(t)} = -\frac{Y'(t)}{Y(t)} = \frac{d \ln Y(t)}{dt} \quad (6)$$

From this expression it can be concluded that there is an exponential relationship between the probability of failure-free operation and the intensity of failures.

$$Y(t) = \exp\left\{-\int_0^t \lambda(x) dx\right\} \quad (7)$$

Based on the expressions given in (6) and (7), we can draw the following conclusion

$$q(t) = Q'(t) = \lambda(t).Y(t) = \lambda(t).\exp\left\{-\int_0^t \lambda(x) dx\right\} \quad (8)$$

The dependence of the variation of the failure intensity on time, where three characteristic sections are distinguished, can be observed in figure 2.

Figure 2

Period I is characterized by high failure intensity due to a number of technological and structural changes. During the time of period I ($0 - t_1$) it is necessary to scrap low-quality elements, remove assembly defects, etc.

Period II has a duration of $(t_1 - t_2)$ and represents the period of normal operation of the boiler/installation, for which λ remains practically unchanged.

Period III, in which $t > t_2$ characterizes the period of intense wear and aging of the elements of boilers and installations.

The correct assessment of failures and the probabilities of their occurrence is of utmost importance to guarantee the long trouble-free life of boilers and installations working with natural gas.

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